

FACTORS FOR FORMING AND IMPROVING WRITING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the difficulties in learning writing skills in English language learners and the key factors in overcoming them.

In the modern English language teaching methodology, the concepts of "written speech" and "writing" are distinguished. We know that communication consists of oral and written speech. If the components of oral speech are communication through listening and speaking, communication is also through written speech. The component of written speech includes reading and writing. Writing is an integral component of written speech.

Writing is also a speech activity through which information is exchanged. Writing plays an important role in teaching English. Through it, information is given to others, through writing we preserve information for a long time, even for centuries, and pass it on to future generations. Without writing, we would not have preserved so much scientific and historical wealth, we would have been deprived of them.

As you can see from the above, writing is a speech activity and we need to learn it. It is considered a productive speech activity and consists of encoding information and information through writing.

Students of higher education institutions are provided with basic information about the sound side of the language, grammatical structure and vocabulary, in accordance with their age and level of knowledge. Based on this knowledge, the norms of writing and stylistics are taught. The content and size of these are determined in the foreign language subject programs and their contents are described in the textbooks.

For example: a student who has received information on phonetics should be able to consciously distinguish between sounds and letters, vowels and consonants.

Disadvantages of Writing in English Language Learning Today:

- lack of lexical units in written speech;
- inability to connect sentences logically;
- not being able to write down their thoughts in full;

- making grammatical, lexical, phonetic, spelling mistakes during writing;
- lack of writing structure;
- lack of writing experience.

Grammatical lessons should be conducted in such a way that the student can analyze the morphological structure of the word, the meaning and grammatical signs of the word groups, the interrelation of the parts of the sentence and analyze them. Vocabulary training, especially vocabulary training, should be explained in relation to social events and changes in life. In this case, it is advisable for the student to use the materials of the local press and fiction.

Writing and speaking exercises.

Every activity in learning foreign languages is an exercise. All written exercises can be divided into two groups:

1. Writing exercises.
2. Exercises that teach written speech.

The main purpose of performing writing exercises is to develop the ability to correctly express the letters and letter combinations of a foreign language, to compare these letters and letter combinations with sounds, to form and improve the skills of writing words correctly.

The following types of exercises can be performed to develop students' writing skills.

1. Writing words from the text in which sound-letters are consistent with each other.
2. Copy and write from the text, underline the words in which the number of sounds does not correspond to the number of letters.
3. Underline the words from the text with letter combinations corresponding to one sound.
4. Copy and write words with unpronounceable letters from the text.
5. Copy and write words in which one sound is represented by different letters. Exercises performed in this manner are mandatory.
6. Copying letters and letter combinations according to the sample.
7. Writing the given letter or letter combinations in several lines.
8. Copy the text.
9. Copy and write the words with the missing letters or combinations of letters.
10. Copy and write some sentences.
11. Copy and write words with capital letters from the text.
12. Copy and write verbs that run in the specific person.
13. Copy and write adjectives.
14. Copying pronouns.
15. Copy and write prepositional phrases.
16. Conducting various dictations. (Dictations are complex exercises in their own right).
 - a) remember what he saw (a letter, word, sentence is written on the board, read, then copied).
 - b) remember what he heard (sound, word, sentence).
 - c) listening and memorizing writing (letter combination, word, sentence, text).
 - g) creative dictation (memorized word, poem, text).

Written speaking exercises are more complicated than writing exercises. This type of exercise requires students to have phonetic, lexical and grammatical knowledge. Written

speech exercises are performed mainly on the basis of the topics covered. In the textbooks, assignments on written speech are also given.

1. Making questions about the text and answering them in writing.
2. Writing the content of the text.
3. Change the person of the verb in the text.
4. Change the tense of the verb in the text.
5. Written description of pictures related to the topic.
6. Write down the meaning of the story you heard.
7. Write an essay on a topic.
8. Shortening the text.

Writing a letter can take a central place in the teaching of written speech. Therefore, the student should determine the content of the letter, collect the necessary model and vocabulary, and teach the rules of writing a letter. When writing a letter, students should use speech units that they have learned orally. We include the following exercises aimed at developing graphic skills:

1. Exercises for writing simple and complex letters separately.

- a) a letter in English that fully or partially corresponds to the Uzbek language, for example: M m, r, d;
 - b) imperative but having separate elements j, you, X x, written differently S s, Cc, H h, Ee, etc.
- 2) Letter combinations representing one sound: т,ч,ш, and exercises for writing complex sound diphthongs and triphthongs.
 - 3) Exercises of moving individual words in text, sentences.
 - 4) Exercises such as letter analysis of individual letter combinations, words, sentences, etc.

Strengthening the visual-graphic motor-speech motor connections of letters and letter combinations plays an important role in the formation of speaking skills, so it should be done in all written exercises.

An important part of learning written speech is teaching spelling skills. Formation of orthographic skills in language learners is the goal of teaching writing.

The orthographic system of the English language is based on the following three principles.

- 1) Phonetic, when the letters correspond exactly to the sounds, for example:

hey, we

- 2) If a grammatical (morphological) entry is determined based on a grammatical rule, phonetic rules are excluded in the pronunciation of one letter (pronunciation change of one letter), for example:

There, out, he, is.

- 3) Historical (traditional) example: one

Phonetic and morphological principles are considered to be the leading principles in English orthography, so it is necessary to pay attention to them in the formation of orthographic skills. Grammatical and orthographic teaching should be parallel with the teaching of writing exercises that strengthen grammatical knowledge in written form. To carry out these exercises, it is advisable to use grammatical exercises such as transformation

corresponding to grammatical rules, prepositions corresponding to the relevant grammatical rule, filling in the following sentences and copying the text.

Written lesson exercises are a means of teaching the correct spelling of words and their elements (stems and suffixes).

These types of exercises include:

1. Analysis exercises on word elements
2. Exercises to divide the word into groups according to different form elements (one-stem same suffix, homographic word, etc.).

In learning to write, it is important to take into account the special adaptation of some sound letters. They include, firstly, the combination of sound with letter combinations, for example, the sound [S] is combined with the letter combination ч in writing. School, S + QU (Square), the second sound is invisible in the writing by means of various graphic signs [i]; the sound is represented by letter combinations ee, ea, because the sound-letter interference in the native language does not match at all in the two languages, for example: the presence of unpronounceable letters in the word (who, what, where), this situation is not typical for the native language.

The above and other situations in the graphic activity system of the mother tongue and the English language cause an increase in the number of orthographic errors in the written speech of language learners. Performing grammar and lexical-oriented and conditional-speech writing exercises serves to develop orthographic and graphic skills.

It is known above that elementary skills of written speech (writing a letter to peers abroad.

Conclusion. The types of written exercises listed above belong to the category of communicative written exercises. The last of the above exercises is more important to achieve the goal of written speech. Each of the above exercises has a purpose and is defined. These types of exercises are key factors in overcoming difficulties in English writing skills.

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